

Dominate wind direction: velocity, frequency and wind direction

The wind rose for Al Fayyum shows how many hours per year the wind blows from the indicated direction.

Wind

23 km/h from N

North/west winter wind direction and north/east summer direction

El Faiyum, **Egypt** - Seasons graph and Earth's orbit

- Events**
- ▲ Today
 - ▲ December solstice
 - ▲ March equinox
 - ▲ June solstice
 - ▲ September equinox
 - ▲ Perihelion [?]
 - ▲ Aphelion [?]
- Earth's orbit**
- This year
 - Min. years 1600-2600 [?]
 - Max. years 1600-2600 [?]
 - Variation, years 1600-2600
- Seasons**
- Winter
 - Spring
 - Summer
 - Fall

Notes: Earth's orbit is highly exaggerated for illustrative purposes. Change [preferences](#).

Size: + - Reset

Next Previous

Event	Date	Time to
December solstice	2020-12-21 12:02	113d 12h 13min
March equinox	2021-03-20 11:37	202d 11h 48min
June solstice	2021-06-21 05:32	295d 5h 43min
September equinox	2020-09-22 15:31	23d 15h 42min

El Faiyum, **Egypt** - Solar energy and surface meteorology

El Faiyum, **Egypt** - Sun path diagram

Sun path

- Today
- June solstice
- December solstice
- Annual variation
- Equinox (March and September)

Sunrise/sunset

- Sunrise
- Sunset

Time

- 00-02
- 03-05
- 06-08
- 09-11
- 12-14
- 15-17
- 18-20
- 21-23

El Faiyum, [Egypt](#) - Solar energy and surface meteorology

Variable	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII
Insolation, kWh/m ² /day	3.21	4.01	5.27	6.68	7.49	8.16	8.01	7.43	6.22	4.83	3.59	2.98
Clearness, 0 - 1	0.54	0.55	0.60	0.65	0.68	0.72	0.72	0.71	0.67	0.62	0.57	0.53
Temperature, °C	12.97	13.60	16.49	21.18	24.77	27.30	28.92	28.82	26.73	22.86	18.69	14.43
Wind speed, m/s	4.33	4.56	4.74	4.77	4.88	4.86	4.81	4.74	4.78	4.61	4.22	4.30
Precipitation, mm	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Wet days, d	2.3	1.9	1.3	0.5	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.7	1.7

These data were obtained from the NASA Langley Research Center Atmospheric Science Data Center; New et al. 2002

Notes: [Help](#). Change [preferences](#).

New! [Gaisma Planet](#) - Interactive Climate and Environment Imagery Viewer

El Faiyum, [Egypt](#) - Basic information

Latitude: +29.31 (29°18'36"N)

Longitude: +30.84 (30°50'24"E)

Base time zone: UTC+2 hours [?]

Local time: 23:50:01

Country: [Egypt](#)

Continent: [Africa](#)

Sub-region: [Northern Africa](#)

Distance: ~230 km (from your IP)

Altitude: ~20 m

[El Faiyum, nearby locations](#)

Change [preferences](#).

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Sun & wind Diagrams for the area

Map of the two ecolodges

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